

Supplementary material – data extraction form

This data extraction form is developed from Cochrane’s “Data collection form for intervention reviews: RCTs and non-RCTs” (1)

General Information

Date form completed (<i>dd/mm/yyyy</i>)		26-09-2022	
Name/ID of person extracting data		MDL	
Author(s)		McGregor et al.	
Country		England	
Publication year		2011	
Title of article		ISSLS Prize Winner: Function After Spinal Treatment, Exercise, and Rehabilitation (FASTER)	
Title of journal		Spine	
Volume 36	Issue 21	Pages 1711-1720	
Publication type (<i>e.g. full report, abstract, letter</i>)		Scientific article	

Study eligibility

Study Characteristics	Eligibility criteria <i>There are no restrictions on the types of study.</i>				Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
		Yes	No	Unclear	
Type of study	Randomised Controlled Trial	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1712
	Quasi-randomised Controlled Trial	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Controlled Before and After Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
	Other design (specify):	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	
Participants		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1712
Types of intervention	Rehabilitation program and an educational booklet	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1711, 1712, 1718
Types of comparison	Usual care	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1712
Types of outcome measures	Pain, function disability /status, quality of life,	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	p. 1711, 1713, 1716, 1717
INCLUDE <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>		EXCLUDE <input type="checkbox"/>			

Characteristics of included studies

Methods

	Descriptions as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Aim of study (e.g. efficacy, equivalence, pragmatic)	The objective of this factorial randomized controlled trial function after spinal treatment, exercise, and rehabilitation (FASTER) was to evaluate the benefits of a rehabilitation program and an education booklet for the postoperative management of patients undergoing discectomy or lateral nerve root decompression, each compared with “usual care.”	p. 1712
Design (e.g. parallel, crossover, non-RCT)	Multicenter, parallel group, factorial, randomized controlled trial	p. 1712
Unit of allocation (by individuals, cluster/groups or body parts)	Randomized using a 2 × 2 factorial design to receive: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Factor 1—either a 6-week program of postoperative rehabilitation or the relevant surgeon’s usual postoperative care (according to the surgeon’s discretion and routine practice): • Factor 2—either an educational booklet (“Your Back operation”), or the surgeon’s usual advice. 	p. 1712
Start date	June 2005	p. 1713
End date	March 2009	p. 1713
Ethical approval needed/ obtained for study	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear The study was approved by Hammersmith and Queen Charlotte’s and Chelsea Hospitals Research Ethics Committee, with site approval for seven hospitals in the West London Region.	p. 1712

Participants

	Description <i>Include comparative information for each intervention or comparison group if available</i>	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Setting (including location and social context)	Seven different hospitals	p. 1713
Inclusion criteria	Eligible patients included those awaiting spinal surgery with either (a) signs, symptoms, and radiological evidence of lateral nerve root compression, that is, patients presenting with radicular pain with an associated neurological deficit or with neurogenic claudication (pain in the buttock, thigh, or leg that improves with rest), or (b) lumbar disc prolapse, that is, patients with root symptoms and signs and MRI confirmation of lumbar disc herniation.	p. 1712

Exclusion criteria	<p>Patients presenting with any of the following were excluded from participation; any condition where either the intervention or the rehabilitation may have an adverse effect on the individual; previous spinal surgery; spinal surgery where a fusion procedure was planned because of the unknown hazards of the activity program for this type of surgery; pregnant women; inadequate ability to complete the trial assessment forms; unable to attend or unsuitable for rehabilitation classes.</p> <p>After poor compliance with return of baseline forms at the start of the trial, patients were only allocated a trial number and treatment group after successful completion of these forms; those not complying were removed from the trial.</p>	p. 1712
Informed consent obtained	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Unclear	Written informed consent obtained p. 1712

Intervention group – Rehabilitation Program

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	<p>6-week program of postoperative rehabilitation</p> <p>Type: Rehabilitation Program</p> <p>Content: Patients in the rehabilitation arms were invited to commence the intervention 6 to 8 weeks after their surgery. The program comprised 12 standardized 1-hour classes run twice weekly by an experienced physiotherapist. They included general aerobic fitness work; stretching; stability exercises; strengthening and endurance training for the back, abdominal, and leg muscles; ergonomic training; advice on lifting and setting targets; and self-motivation along with an open group discussion at the end of each class. Compliance was based on attendance records, and the quality and content of the classes were reviewed regularly. Any clustering effects due to therapist or treatment center were considered negligible because of the large number of physiotherapists running classes, thus patients were routinely crossing between therapists.</p>	p. 1712
No. randomized to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	<p>N=86 (M:37, F:49)</p> <p>Mean age = 54</p>	<p>p. 1715</p> <p>p. 1715 table 1</p>

Intervention group – Educational Booklet

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Educational Booklet	p. 1712
No. randomized to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=70 (M:36, F:34) Mean age = 53	p. 1715 p. 1715 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Type: Educational Booklet. Content: Patients received a copy of “Your Back operation” on discharge from the hospital.	p. 1712

Intervention group – Rehabilitation Program + Educational Booklet

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Rehab + Educational Booklet	p. 1715 table 1
No. randomized to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=91 (M:47; F:44) Mean age = 53	p. 1715 table 1

Control group

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Group name	Usual care	
No. randomized to group (specify whether no. people or clusters)	N=91 (M:39, F:52) Mean age = 55	p. 1715 p. 1715 table 1
Description (include sufficient detail for replication, e.g. content, dose, components)	Usual care: Patients receiving usual care were managed according to the relevant surgeon’s usual practice. This is varied and limited.	p. 1711, 1712, 1714, 1715, 1716, 1717

Outcomes

Outcome 1

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Pain	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Visual Analog Scale (VAS) No difference	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713

Outcome 2

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Function disability /status	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Outcome, function disability /status ODI No differenxe	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713

Outcome 3

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Quality of life	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	EuroQol-5 Dimension health questionnaire (EQ-5D) Results not reported	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713

Outcome 4

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (pg & ¶/fig/table/other)
Outcome name	Mental health	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713

Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Hospital anxiety and depression (HADS) questionnaire; Fear Avoidance Beliefs Questionnaire (FABQ)	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713
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Outcome 5

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Outcome name	Overall health	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713
Outcome definition (<i>with diagnostic criteria if relevant</i>)	Visual Analog Scale (VAS)	Abstract, p. 1712, 1713

Follow up

Follow up	12 months	p. 1714 Figure 1
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Conclusion

	Description as stated in report/paper	Location in text or source (<i>pg & ¶/fig/table/other</i>)
Conclusion	<p>Results: Three hundred thirty-eight patients were recruited into the study and measurements were obtained preoperatively and then repeated at 6 weeks, 3, 6, 9 and 12 months postoperatively. Twelve months postoperatively the observed effect of rehabilitation on ODI was -2.7 (95% CI: -6.8 to 1.5) and the effect of booklet was 2.7 (95% CI: -1.5 to 6.9). Conclusion: This study found that neither intervention had a significant impact on long-term outcome.</p> <p>Clearly, the provision of education for patients requires greater consideration and should be patient rather than clinician led, focusing on what patients need to know rather than what we feel confident telling them. It has also become apparent that type of surgery may impact on type of postoperative rehabilitation and this requires further exploration. Consequently, this study can find no support for the provision of postoperative rehabilitation or educational interventions.</p>	<p>Abstract, p. 1714</p> <p>p. 1718</p>

References

1. Cochrane. Data collection form for intervention reviews for RCTs and non-RCTs - template [Internet]. The Cochrane Collaboration. 2022 [cited 2022 Sep 15]. Available from: <https://dplp.cochrane.org/data-extraction-forms>